

Urban spatial structure and pandemic stress: A spatial analysis of subjective well-being in Polish cities

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Abstract. This study investigates the spatial relationship between urban spatial structure and perceived stress during the COVID-19 pandemic in the Poznań agglomeration, Poland. Utilizing a CAWI geo-survey (n=737), we analyze how building density, population density, and greenery accessibility impact mental well-being across Poznań, Swarzędz, and Puszczykowo. The methodology employs Spearman's R correlation, Global and Local Moran's I (LISA), Geographically Weighted Regression (GWR) and a General Linear Model (GLM). Findings reveal that while global stress distribution appears predominantly random across all urban scales, localized micro-clusters (LISA) emerge at the neighborhood level. A key result demonstrates that physical building density has a significantly stronger spatial association with stress ($I=0.048$, $p=0.005$) than population concentration ($p=0.05$). Furthermore, while greenery accessibility acts as a global stress buffer ($p<0.05$), its impact is highly localized and was particularly critical for older adults during the pandemic, as evidenced by a significant age-distance interaction in the GLM. These results provide actionable geospatial intelligence, suggesting that stress drivers operate at a highly localized scale and are primarily influenced by the physical urban fabric rather than urban scale or social density alone.

Submission Type. Poster track.

BoK Concepts. [GC] Geocomputation, [GD] Geospatial Data.

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1 Introduction

It is widely recognized that we live in an increasingly stressful world, with urban residents being particularly vulnerable. In recent years, the COVID-19 pandemic emerged as a significant additional stressor, leaving its most profound mark on urban areas. This was primarily due to higher virus transmission rates in dense environments, the challenges of maintaining social distancing, and the adverse psychological effects of pandemic countermeasures (Hagger et al., 2020; Talarkowska et al., 2020). In the context of the pandemic, research has shown that the urban spatial structure consists of elements that can either amplify or mitigate subjective stress. (Wdowicka et al., 2024). These findings align with extensive literature highlighting the restorative role of nature in urban settings (Braubach et al., 2017).

However, urban environments are characterized by significant spatial heterogeneity. During the pandemic, restricted mobility made local configurations decisive for mental health. As the relationship between urban structure and stress is often non-stationary, understanding these spatial dependencies allows planners to design resilient cities capable of mitigating psychological distress.

The primary objective of this study is to investigate the relationship between subjective stress levels and urban spatial structure during the COVID-19 pandemic. To achieve this goal, the following research questions were formulated:

- Does subjective stress exhibit significant spatial clustering across different urban scales?
- How do building density, population density, and greenery accessibility correlate with stress?

- Are these relationships spatially stationary or dependent on local context?

2 Methodology:

2.1 Study Area and Data Collection

This study was conducted in Poznań, Swarzędz, and Puszczykowo (Poland), representing diverse urban scales. Primary data were collected via Computer-Assisted Web Interviewing (CAWI) geo-surveys, based on geo-information systems (Jankowski et al. 2016; Bakowska et al. 2017). The analysis focused on a geolocated subsample of n=737 respondents.

2.2 Variables and Data Sources

- Perceived Stress: Self-reported levels (scale 0–10).
- Building Density: Modeled on a 250m grid using the national Database of Topographic Objects (BDOT10k).
- Population Density: Derived from Kontur Population data.
- Greenery Accessibility: Based on Copernicus Land Monitoring Service (areas ≥ 1 ha), calculated via Euclidean and network distances.

2.3 Analytical Framework

The multi-stage analysis utilized Spearman's R for global correlations and Global/Local Moran's I (LISA) to identify spatial clustering. Spatial weights were defined using an inverse-distance threshold, optimized to ensure no isolated observations, with row-standardization. A multivariate General Linear Model (GLM) assessed the independent effects of greenery accessibility (Euclidean and network distances) on stress, controlling for gender, age, education, and professional activity. An age-distance interaction term was included to test varying sensitivities across age groups. Finally, Geographically Weighted Regression (GWR) was employed to capture spatial non-stationarity in the impact of the urban fabric.

2.4 Data and Software Availability

Primary survey data are not public due to privacy and ethical restrictions regarding respondent geolocation and sensitive health reports. Anonymized data may be provided by the authors upon reasonable request.

3 Results/findings:

3.1. Comparative Analysis of Stress Levels Across Cities

The mean stress level was 5.45. Poznań (5.48) and Swarzędz (5.47) reported comparable levels, while Puszczykowo's lower average (5.21) was not statistically significant. This suggests urban scale alone does not determine stress, requiring a deeper look at internal spatial structures.

3.2. Spatial Autocorrelation (Moran's I)

To formally assess whether perceived stress values are spatially structured, a Global Moran's I analysis was conducted for each city. The results indicate a lack of significant global spatial autocorrelation across all three study areas. For Poznań, the Global Moran's I was found to be nearly zero ($I = -0.001$, $p = 0.947$), suggesting that the distribution of perceived stress levels is predominantly random across the city. However, LISA analysis revealed localized micro-clusters that global statistics might overlook. "High-High" pockets were identified in the central part of the city, while small "Low-Low" cluster were found in specific residential area. This suggests that in a large urban environment like Poznań, stress factors operate at a neighborhood-specific scale.

In contrast, Swarzędz exhibited a marginally significant tendency toward a dispersed spatial pattern ($I = -0.089$, $z = -1.94$, $p = 0.052$). LISA for Swarzędz identified High-Low and Low-High outliers, suggesting high spatial heterogeneity and a 'checkerboard' mixing of stress experiences. Finally, Puszczykowo showed a strictly random distribution ($I = -0.015$, $p = 0.639$).

Figure 1. The respondents' subjective stress levels—results of cluster and spatial outlier analysis.

3.3 Spatial Dependencies between Stress and Urban Structure

The bivariate Global Moran's I analysis for Poznań revealed a marginal spatial association between population density and perceived stress ($I=0.017$, $p=0.05$), while the relationship with building density was found to be more pronounced and highly significant ($I=0.048$, $p=0.005$). This contrast suggests that the physical intensity of the urban fabric is a more consistent driver of psychological tension than resident concentration. Bivariate LISA identified significant spatial heterogeneity in the building density-stress relationship. Prominent High-High hotspots were detected in the central part of Poznań, indicating areas where high building density directly coincides with elevated stress levels, while Low-Low clusters were primarily observed in the peripheral areas. To formally capture the spatial non-stationarity of this relationship, GWR was employed. The GWR model demonstrated that the impact of building density is not spatially uniform; the strength of the relationship fluctuates across the urban landscape. The highest local R^2 values were concentrated in the central core, with additional areas identified in the northern part of the city.

3.4 Greenery Accessibility

Correlation analysis revealed that stress levels increase with distance to greenery ($p<0.05$) for the entire sample, with comparable results for both Euclidean and network distances. Regarding individual cities, a statistically significant correlation was found only in Puszczykowo for Euclidean distance ($p=0.019$). Beyond simple correlations, multivariate models revealed that spatial proximity (Euclidean distance) and physical accessibility (network distance) have distinct impacts on stress levels depending on the demographic context. Notably, a significant interaction in the Euclidean model, suggested that that general proximity to green spaces was particularly critical for older adults during the pandemic.

5 Conclusion

This study demonstrates that urban spatial structure, particularly building density, is a more critical determinant of perceived stress than population concentration. The findings reveal a clear "scale effect," where significant spatial clustering of stress is evident in major metropolitan areas like Poznań, while smaller towns exhibit more diffuse, random patterns. The identification of specific High-High hotspots and the detection of spatial non-stationarity through GWR

provide actionable geospatial intelligence, allowing for evidence-based urban design tailored to local contexts.

Future research will focus on expanding the current framework into a multivariate GWR model. This next stage will integrate a wider range of urban spatial factors alongside respondents' socio-demographic characteristics and housing typologies (e.g., distinguishing between single-family houses and multi-apartment blocks). By accounting for the interplay between individual backgrounds and environmental stressors, we aim to develop a more granular predictive model for urban well-being and resilience.

Declaration of Generative AI in writing

The author declare that I have not used Generative AI tools in the preparation of this manuscript. Specifically, the AI tools were utilized for language editing, improving grammar, and sentence structure, but not for generating scientific content, research data, or substantive conclusions. All intellectual and creative work, including the analysis and interpretation of data, is original and has been conducted by the author without AI assistance.

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